

Impact of the Tourism Industry Scenarios in Urban Economy: (Case Study Tabriz)

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Received: 3 December 2020 Reviewed: 8 December 2020 Revised: 17 December 2020 Accept: 6 January 2021</p>	<p>Purpose: The tourism industry, especially in its urban dimension, has a special place in the economies of countries and its effects and consequences are evident in all dimensions. Cities are considered as tourist places due to their structure, texture and identity, and one of the components of economic development of cities and its result in countries is tourism.</p> <p>Methodology: To do this, in addition to library studies, interviews with experts and professors in the field of tourism and economics have been conducted in order to identify the components affecting tourism. Based on the research findings from statistical analysis based on SPSS and Mini Tab software, different scenarios for the development of tourism in Tabriz have been designed in accordance with Micmac software and based on them, the necessary solutions have been provided. To do this, by designing a questionnaire to collect data, by analyzing the information obtained, input factors in four areas of strategic planning, tourism potentials, regional conditions and infrastructure facilities and effective consequences on the problem in two economic areas. And tourism consequences are categorized.</p> <p>Findings: Using the results, probable, plausible and possible scenarios are identified and finally suggestions for economic development of tourism in Tabriz based on these scenarios are expressed. The results show that despite the many conditions and capabilities in the city of Tabriz, programs and infrastructure facilities are still not suitable for tourism development and, consequently, the prosperity of the urban economy in this area.</p> <p>Originality/Value: The main purpose of this study is to explain the impact and importance of the tourism industry in the flourishing of the urban economy and the purpose of its implementation in the metropolis of Tabriz is to study tourism scenarios in the future of Tabriz urban economy.</p>
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1. Introduction

Taking into account advances in economic thought, analysis and in applied methods, it pays attention to relevant traditional topics in tourism economics as well as exciting emerging topics in this field — topics which are expected to be of continuing importance. Contributions provide applications of economic analysis to tourism policy and constructive assessment of contemporary thought about tourism economics [1]. Although the tourism industry cannot play a full role in the prosperity of the city's economy, but it has direct and indirect positive impact on the economy of communities. The direct effects of the tourism industry arise from the initial expenditure of tourists on consumer goods and services. This part of the effects creates direct employment and foreign exchange earnings through the production and sale of goods and services to tourists [2]. Tourism in cities includes more cultural, historical and special attractions than natural attractions. These attractions have a greater impact on the minds and desires of tourists and become one of the sources of regional and macro-income generation of governments and, by nature, residents of the area. Development of human resources, trade balance, employment etc. is the most important economic consequences of urban tourism. Investigating the economic issues resulting from appropriate tourism, effective forecasting methods in this regard and the need for proper planning to achieve this, is the main process of this paper, especially in metropolitan city such as Tabriz, where these attractions It has more manifestations and can be the beginning of extensive changes in the urban economy and macroeconomics of Iran, and as a result, entering this field and presenting future plans is one of the requirements for paying attention to this problem. The continuation of this article includes a review of the research background related to this issue, theoretical foundations, research method, research findings including statistical analysis and futurism and conclusions from those findings and suggestions about the future of Tabriz urban economy according to the issues of the tourism industry.

2. Literature review

Studies examining the relationship between tourism and economic growth have found a positive relationship, in both developing and developed economies. [3], [4], [5]. In anticipation of recovery in the tourism industry post COVID-19, one study examines the economic impact of tourism on economic growth and other macroeconomic variables in a panel of 46 countries. Using system-GMM estimation, this study finds that tourism has a statistically significant positive effect on economic growth. It is found that tourism specialization at higher levels dampens the positive effect on growth. The results suggest that policy makers should be measured in their approach as they navigate their economies post-COVID-19 when the tourism industry is in the recovery phase [6]. Another study proposes a general standard for the circular economy (CE), and estimates a multidimensional parametric index composed of eight components, which is in line with the principles of a circular economy. The index is regressed on a number of indicators influencing the level and development of circular economy. The empirical analysis is based on data from 273 municipalities in Sweden observed 2012–18. The results suggest that there are significant differences between the municipalities in the CE index and its sub-components [7]. Understanding the motivations and characteristics of collective transport users in contemporary cities may contribute to promote more sustainable forms of tourism. Based on an extensive questionnaire to international tourists in Barcelona, one study employs a multinomial logistic regression to explore the links among visitors' characteristics, motivations, and means of transportation, while an ordinal logistic regression is applied to investigate whether the preference for collective transport has an impact on the satisfaction with the trip. The results show that professional travelers are more oriented to the use of private cars, but they prefer collective transports when the length of stay is higher and combined with

other trip motivations. This study puts forward policy implications and suggestions for future research directions, in particular regarding the utilization of non-motorized forms of transportation cities [8].

Socio-economic sustainability for tourism workers does not play a prominent role in contemporary tourism Economic impact studies. Rather, to promote economic growth paradigms, the focus lies on aggregated employment and income effects. To better understand tourism's contribution this study assesses tourism's socio-economic impact by focusing on mesa-level perspectives from major tourism institutions that are complemented with macro-level results gained through an occupation-based Input-Output model [9]. After the economic liberalization in mid-2000, Tanzania has assumed that tourism growth spurs economic growth due to the consistent significant contribution of tourism sector to the country's annual income. However, there are limited empirical studies that investigated tourism-economic growth relationship in Tanzania. This study aims to investigate an empirical insight into the actual nature of tourism-economic growth in Tanzania by applying the Granger causality and Wald test methods where annual time series data on international tourism receipt, real Gross Domestic Product, and real effective exchange rate over the period 1989–2018 are used. The study concludes that Tanzania ought to focus on economic strategies that encourage sustainable tourism development as a feasible source of economic growth [10]. Another study examines the relationship between tourism specialization economic growth, and human development in a transition economy. It proffers a conceptual link between tourism specialization and human development through a division of labor framework. The Limited Information Maximum Likelihood (LIML) estimates this relationship's nature in the case of Poland. The study's implications are two testable propositions and two policy options suggesting tourism specialization's potential impact on private and public incomes, which are relevant developmental channels in transition economies [11]. Tourism plays an increasingly critical role in national and urban economies. While tourist spending particularly benefits urban economies, the growth of urban tourism has gradually intensified cities' reliance on external resources and significantly influenced resource-supplying areas [12, 13]. One study adopts the concept of urban land teleconnections (ULTs) to discuss how the cultural ecosystem services in the tourism industry have affected distant areas in general and how the increased tourist flow has intensified Taipei's dependence on external resources and challenged its urban sustainability in particular. An emerge-based analysis is conducted to evaluate the contribution of material flows triggered by urban tourism into the urban ecological-economic system and to demonstrate how urban tourism has increased the city's reliance on external distant areas. The analysis highlights the biophysical value created by external resources in the economic system [14, 15].

A paper aims to examine the role of economic policy uncertainty (EPU) on tourism investments across the samples of OECD, non-OECD, high-income, upper-middle-income, and low-income economies. The findings from the Common Correlated Effects Mean Group (CCEMG) and the Group Mean approaches show that the EPU has a significant negative impact on tourism investments across the panels. Moreover, other estimates suggest that economic development, financial development, and trade positively contribute to tourism investments [16]. Future study is vital now more than ever for countries to develop tourism and attract international tourists. Modern methods of future study, especially scenario building, are helpful in addressing issues at the national and regional scale because of their flexible strategies. According to the applied nature of the study, data were collected in two ways: reviewing previous studies and using questionnaires. The data were analyzed using MICMAC analysis and Scenario Wizard software. The results of the MICMAC method indicated that 10 variables have key/predominant roles in terms of influence in the development system of Iran's tourism market. The

results of the Scenario-Wizard method indicated that four scenarios have strong consistencies, and among those, only one is a driver that has ideal and desirable characteristics and conditions for implementation [17]. Residents are one of the most valuable assets for a tourist destination, so their perceptions of tourism constitute a crucial pillar for designing tourism development strategies that promote sustainable development. A paper investigates the determinants of both resident perception and willingness to support tourism development. The proposed model, which combines the social exchange theory (SET) and place attachment theory (PAT), was tested via structural equation modeling (SEM) using data collected from 409 residents of Isfahan. This article tests the impact of resident perception of economic crisis on their perception of tourism and their willingness to support its development. Results indicate that those who perceive a higher level of economic crisis are more likely to view the impacts of tourism positively and support its development [18]. For urban areas, Tourism Carrying Capacity (TCC) can be defined as the abilities of a destination to absorb and manage increasing tourism activities without a degradation in the tourism sector of the urban economy. To optimize the concept and assessment of TCC, a paper develops a dynamic carrying capacity model including 3 subsystems and 47 variables by System Dynamic (SD) method from a macroscopic perspective. Taking the top nine urban tourism destinations in China as the objects of the study, paper compares how government investments in tourism resource, environmental protection, economy and infrastructure impact tourism growth through four scenarios. The results indicate that environment scenario simulation contributes to both TCC and tourism economic growth; the economic scenario simulation can increase the overall TCC, but harms to tourism economic growth compared with other scenarios; the resource scenario simulation has no significant change in TCC compared with the current scenario [19].

Another paper studies the dynamics of economic growth and tourism evolution for 80 countries during the period 1995–2016. The variables representing economic and tourism growth are growth rates of per capita GDP and international tourist arrivals per inhabitant respectively. Using the concept of economic regime, the paper introduces a notion of distance between the dynamical paths of different countries [20]. The aim of a paper is to present a methodology for the decomposition of economic growth by industry which allows between provinces comparisons in Iran. The authors use the growth of real GDP per capita as a measure of economic growth and disaggregate it into economic growth created by tourism and economic growth created by other industries. A Growth Decomposition Method (GDM) is used for measuring the contribution of tourism to an economy's growth for Iran from period 2005–2014. The results show that the impact of tourism on economic growth is positive [21].

3. Data and Methodology

3.1. Data

The spatial scope of this research is the geographical area of Tabriz. If necessary, some information and national and provincial conditions have been used in order to find effective factors. The results of this research explain the effective factors of tourism industry in the future economic growth of Tabriz. In order to conduct research and collect the information needed to answer the research questions, interview and preparation of a questionnaire and evaluate the status of the case study; the document mining method has been used. For this purpose, the opinions of experts and specialists in the field of tourism of East Azerbaijan province and professors of tourism and economics of the province's universities and tourism information available in the tourism sites of Tabriz Municipality and the Cultural Heritage, Handicrafts and Tourism Organization of East Azerbaijan Province have been used. In addition, the

data extracted from the comprehensive system of Tabriz city plan. The statistical population of this research is experts and specialists in the fields of economics and tourism of Tabriz city and East Azerbaijan province, including the Tourism Organization of the General Directorate of Cultural Heritage, Tourism and Handicrafts, and Tabriz Municipality. The reason for choosing the statistical population is the possibility of access to existing data and detailed familiarity with the case study of the research.

3.2. Methodology

With the limitations of this research and the limitation of the consequences of this research to the economic field, and through the Cochran's sample formula, 48 people from the statistical community have been selected to collect data and perform tests. Using a questionnaire, the effectiveness of each of the factors and issues of tourism in Tabriz was assessed to determine the importance of each factor in tourism. For this purpose, a suitable design of research thematic questions was performed and statistical samples were distributed among individuals. Out of 48 questionnaires, 36 questionnaires were completed and the analysis phase began. The questionnaire is designed from 20 questions, which are divided into 4 categories as input factors including: strategic planning, historical-cultural potentials, regional conditions, infrastructure facilities and two output factors including: tourism outcome and economic consequences, is closed.

Data analysis is done in two areas of statistics and optimization. In the statistical field, using frequency tables, charts and central indicators and dispersion, a picture of the study population is described. In line with the objectives of the research, in terms of size and significance, hypothesis tests necessary to generalize the results of statistical samples to the community have been analyzed. Futuristic methods have been used to optimally analyze the results and present the necessary scenarios. SPSS and Minitab software were used for statistical analysis of data and Micmac software was used for processing scenarios. In drawing scenarios, three levels of possible future, plausible future and probable future are evaluated [22].

3.2.1. Possible Futures

This type of future includes all the situations that may occur in the future. This spectrum of futures is a collection of images that man has in mind for his future and is mainly imaginative and the result of the depiction of the human mind. These futures are beyond today's human knowledge and science.

3.2.2. Plausible Futures

It includes those futures that can emerge in the future based on current human knowledge, and unlike possible futures that contradict current human principles and knowledge, these futures are based on these principles. Plausible futures are a subset of possible futures.

3.2.3. Probable Futures

Refers to futures that are likely to be realized. These futures are subsets of plausible futures.

In scenario writing for the future, a combination of possible, probable and plausible futures is drawn as the desired future, and to achieve that future, different scenarios are developed that form a basket of contradictory, proportionate, different and similar scenarios.

4. Results and discussion

Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used to determine the reliability of the questionnaire in this study. This test, the result of which is a coefficient called Cronbach's alpha, is used for a reliability test or a questionnaire that is designed as a Likert scale and the answers are multiple-choice. The number of variables is equal to the number of questions in the questionnaire. The order of the items (in terms of question scores) is not important for the Cronbach's alpha coefficient, because this coefficient performs calculations based on variance [23]:

$$\alpha = \left(\frac{k}{k-1}\right) \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k S_i^2}{S^2}\right) \quad (1)$$

Where in, k, number of questions, S^2 , the variance is the sum of the scores of each respondent, and S_i^2 the variance of the scores is related to question number i. For reliable classification of input and output variables, Cronbach's alpha test was performed for each of the questions. According to Table 1, the alpha value of all questions is greater than 0.7. Also, with the statistical analysis performed by Minitab software according to Table 2, the alpha value of 0.77 was obtained, which values greater than 0.7 for the Cronbach's coefficient show that the questionnaire has good reliability.

Table 1. Assessing the reliability of the questions based on the alpha coefficient.

variable	mean	St Dev	Total Corr	Corr	Alpha Cronbach
x1	57.943	7.646	0.2939	0.7931	0.7681
x2	57.971	7.524	0.3494	0.7124	0.7646
x3	57.514	7.751	0.2269	0.4375	0.7717
x4	59.286	7.497	0.3874	0.7767	0.7616
x5	57.971	7.683	0.2033	0.7742	0.7754
x6	59.400	7.508	0.3641	0.7914	0.7634
x7	57.229	7.788	0.2745	0.6449	0.7697
x8	59.514	7.536	0.3306	0.6984	0.7661
x9	59.229	7.720	0.2051	0.5450	0.7740
x10	59.571	7.766	0.1727	0.5778	0.7754
x11	59.400	7.582	0.4439	0.7540	0.7594
x12	59.600	7.709	0.2784	0.8263	0.7689
x13	59.429	7.281	0.6835	0.7796	0.7402
x14	59.857	7.519	0.5222	0.7961	0.7547
x15	59.343	7.731	0.2287	0.7544	0.7718
x16	57.429	7.617	0.3555	0.6838	0.7642
x17	58.971	7.633	0.3193	0.7754	0.7664
x18	59.600	7.589	0.3235	0.7636	0.7663
x19	58.086	7.426	0.3913	0.5997	0.7615
x20	57.400	7.562	0.4209	0.7614	0.7600

Table 2. Assessing the reliability of the whole test based on the alpha coefficient

variable	Count	Mean	St Dev
x1	35	3.886	0.900
x2	35	3.857	1.061
x3	35	4.314	0.758
x4	35	2.543	1.039
x5	35	3.857	1.033
x6	35	2.429	1.065
x7	35	4.600	0.553
x8	35	2.314	1.078
x9	35	2.600	0.914
x10	35	2.257	0.852
x11	35	2.429	0.778
x12	35	2.229	0.770
x13	35	2.400	0.946
x14	35	1.971	0.785
x15	35	2.486	0.818
x16	35	4.400	0.847
x17	35	2.857	0.879
x18	35	2.229	0.973
x19	35	3.743	1.172
x20	35	4.429	0.850
Total	35	61.829	7.958

Out of 20 questions, the variables x6, x10, x11, x18 as strategic planning variables, the variables x1, x2, x4, the variables of historical-cultural potentials, the variables x3, x5, x7, the variables of regional conditions and the variables x7, x8, x9, x12 are classified as infrastructure variables (Table 3). The variables x17 and x19 are used as variables of tourism results and the variables x13, x14, x15, x16 and x20 economic consequences in tourism are used as the output factor in the research (Table 4).

Table 3. Classes of input variables

Variables	Type of input factor	Variant class	Average class
X6 X10 X11 X18	Strategic Planning	0.119	2.360
X1 X2 X4	Historical-cultural potentials	0.080	3.417
X3 X5	Regional conditions	0.197	4.070
X7 X8 X9 X12	Infrastructure facilities	0.218	2.928

Table 4. Classes of output variables

Variables	Type of output factor	Variant class	Average class
X17 X19	Tourism outcome	0.217	3.320
X13 X14 X15 X16 X20	Economic consequences	0.059	3.148

According to statistical analysis, regional conditions play a more effective role with an average of 4.07. This indicates that proximity to regional tourist destinations and proximity to tourist countries from the perspective of experts and tourists can have a major impact on the acceptance of tourism in an area (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Comparison of the mean of input variables (Resource: Research Findings)

The variable of historical and cultural potentials also indicates that the existence of these conditions and opportunities is also important in the acceptance of tourism. A value of 3.42 for this category indicates that the respondents have given an above average score for the impact of these potentials on tourism in Tabriz, and on the other hand, the low standard deviation of this category also confirms that this situation is relatively well focused. While the regional condition class with a higher-than-average average with a relatively higher standard deviation indicates that some respondents believed that this class might have an even lower-than-average impact on tourism. In other words, the consensus of experts on the existence of historical and cultural potentials as a relatively appropriate criterion on tourism in Tabriz is more than the good impact of regional conditions on its tourism. The average below the average of the strategic planning class shows that the attention to planning and foresight in the development of tourism in Tabriz in the view of many respondents has been weak. Also, from the point

of view of some, although the facilities and infrastructure have been developed to some extent in accordance with tourism and its requirements, the existence of these conditions is still not appropriate.

The results of output variables show that both consequences of the study of the impact of factors on tourism in Tabriz are moderate. In other words, if tourism scenarios are designed for the city of Tabriz despite the continuation of such conditions; certainly, a suitable and tourism-friendly landscape is not drawn for the city of Tabriz. The low standard deviation of the economic implications category also shows that the consensus of experts on the economic implications of the research design is high. As everyone agrees that the impact of tourism and the need for proper planning for it is necessary to increase the economic potential of the region, they also emphasize that tourism, as it should and perhaps, on the regional economy and its growth and dynamism. Has not made a proper impact.

Based on the analysis of variables and its results, scenarios have been developed in Micmac software. Probable scenarios indicate the occurrence of strong states in the future of Tabriz based on the scores and software analysis, which is given in Table 5. In this situation, planning is done in its original nature, but it is not based on the vision and future principles of tourism. Re-traveling to the city of Tabriz is included in the program of a few tourists. The buildings, historical and traditional areas of Tabriz also have the attraction of attracting tourists, but appropriate scientific and cultural programs for this are weak. Facilities and infrastructure will not be developed in a balanced and proportionate way in the future. The media will play a less informative role in covering tourism news and information than before. The city will be far from modern and electronic, but regional conditions and proximity to tourist countries will be an opportunity for it. In the field of planning, participation in international forums to introduce Tabriz will be very low according to experts; the plans will continue for a while and the plan to travel to Tabriz again will not be seen much. Continuing the trend of cross-sectional tourism programs, due to the stability of regional conditions, the first and second scenarios, respectively, indicate the disproportionate development of physical and information infrastructure in the current state of historical urban potential; the third scenario also shows the ineffectiveness of cultural potentials, which certainly reflects the lack of information infrastructure. The fourth scenario also states that when the role of planning to encourage tourists to the region is weak, the existence of historical and urban potentials and attractions will not have much effect on attracting tourists; and it is the homogeneous and proportionate development of infrastructure that can encourage tourists to return to the city of Tabriz. Therefore, the consequence of possible scenarios in the future of tourism in Tabriz is the inappropriate economic consequence of this industry in the development of Tabriz and travel to Tabriz as a tourist destination as usual.

Table 5. Probable scenarios in the future of Tabriz tourism

	Planning	Potentials	Infrastructures	Regional Conditions
First Scenario	National and transnational planning: cross-sectional	Ancient traditions and history of Tabriz: Excellent	Hoteling, transportation and leisure centers: Poor	Regional conditions: convenient and opportunity
Second Scenario	National and transnational planning: cross-sectional	Ancient traditions and history of Tabriz: Excellent	Media status: Poor	Regional conditions: convenient and opportunity
Third Scenario	National and transnational planning: cross-sectional	Cultural and scientific conditions: Poor	Hoteling, transportation and leisure centers: Poor	Regional conditions: convenient and opportunity
Forth Scenario	Participation in meetings to recognize Tabriz: a little	Cultural and scientific conditions: Poor	Hoteling, transportation and leisure centers: Poor	Regional conditions: convenient and opportunity

The reasonable expectation is that plausible scenarios according to Table 6 will occur in the future of tourism in Tabriz with a relatively high probability. Given the implications of the system defined in the study, changing attitudes toward planning and infrastructure development can increase belief in the occurrence of such situations. This change includes the preparation of medium-term plans for tourism in line with national development plans, explaining the opportunities and threats to the development of regional tourism, strengthening scientific and cultural programs for tourism growth and development, quantitative and qualitative development of electronics infrastructure, the appropriate development of hotels, resorts, leisure centers and transportation fleet, upgrade media programs and strengthen cyberspace to recognize the city of Tabriz. Realization of plausible scenarios causes balanced economic growth of the region in terms of tourism and destination of Tabriz as one of at least ten tourism hubs in the country among domestic tourists and its introduction as a suitable destination for foreign tourists. In the field of planning, in a situation with more credibility, the possibility of realizing medium-term plans in tourism development along with infrastructure development has a positive effect on economic and tourism outcomes. Also, with less credibility, we can point to the realization of prospects and explain the opportunities and threats to the advancement of tourism in strategic planning, which can have important effects on improving tourism. The rest of the scenarios specify such situations.

Table 6. Plausible scenarios in the future of Tabriz tourism

	Planning	Potentials	Infrastructures	Regional Conditions
First Scenario	National and transnational planning: midterm	Ancient traditions and history of Tabriz: Excellent	Hoteling, transportation and leisure centers: Moderate	Regional conditions: convenient and opportunity
Second Scenario	National and transnational planning: midterm	Ancient traditions and history of Tabriz: Excellent	Electronic infrastructure: common	Regional conditions: convenient and opportunity
Third Scenario	National and transnational planning: midterm	Cultural and scientific conditions: moderate	Electronic infrastructure: common	Regional conditions: convenient and opportunity
Forth Scenario	National and transnational planning: long-term	Cultural and scientific conditions: moderate	Electronic infrastructure: common	Regional conditions: convenient and opportunity
Fifth Scenario	National and transnational planning: longterm	Ancient traditions and history of Tabriz: Excellent	Electronic infrastructure: common	Regional conditions: convenient and opportunity
Sixth Scenario	National and transnational planning: longterm	Ancient traditions and history of Tabriz: Excellent	Cyberspace: Strong	Regional conditions: convenient and opportunity
Seventh Scenario	National and transnational planning: longterm	Cultural and scientific conditions: moderate	Cyberspace: Strong	Regional conditions: convenient and opportunity
Eighth Scenario	National and transnational planning: longterm	Ethnic and tribal conditions: moderate	Cyberspace: Strong	Regional conditions: convenient and opportunity
Ninth Scenario	National and transnational planning: longterm	Ethnic and tribal conditions: moderate	Electronic infrastructure: common	Regional conditions: convenient and opportunity
Tenth Scenario	National and transnational planning: midterm	Ethnic and tribal conditions: moderate	Electronic infrastructure: common	Regional conditions: convenient and opportunity
Eleventh Scenario	National and transnational planning: midterm	Ethnic and tribal conditions: moderate	Electronic infrastructure: common	Climate and geographical location: common
Twelfth Scenario	National and transnational planning: midterm	Ethnic and tribal conditions: moderate	Cyberspace: Strong	Climate and geographical location: common

Possible scenarios with low probability may occur in the future of tourism in Tabriz. According to the analysis of these scenarios in Table 7, given that the development of infrastructure in each city and also the change in attitudes towards programs is a function of time, not much is expected to change these factors in the medium term. Having long-term plans, development of modern tourism support systems, citizenship education in the field of tourism, introduction of the city of Tabriz as a tourism hub and the like require fundamental cultural, social and political changes. We must also keep in mind that in the absence of well-codified tourism plans, some opportunities, such as proximity to tourist countries and

the existence of urban potential, can become a threat to the tourism industry. Although these scenarios are less likely to be realized and effective in the real future, but due to the continuity and stability in the management and planning of the tourism industry can provide economic prosperity and tourism polarization in Tabriz.

Table 7. Possible future scenarios of tourism in Tabriz

	Planning	Potentials	Infrastructures	Regional Conditions	
First Scenario	National and transnational planning: long-term	Ancient traditions and history of Tabriz: Excellent	Hoteling, transportation and leisure centers: strong	Regional conditions: convenient and opportunity	
Second Scenario			Electronic infrastructure: strong		
Third Scenario			Electronic infrastructure: strong		
Forth Scenario	Participation in meetings to recognize Tabriz: Moderate	Citizenship and tourism customs: Medium	Hoteling, transportation and leisure centers: strong		
Fifth Scenario			Hoteling, transportation and leisure centers: strong		
Sixth Scenario			Electronic infrastructure: strong		
Seventh Scenario	Participation in meetings to recognize Tabriz: Extensive	Ancient traditions and history of Tabriz: Excellent	Electronic infrastructure: strong		
Eighth Scenario			Hoteling, transportation and leisure centers: strong		
Ninth Scenario			Hoteling, transportation and leisure centers: strong		
Tenth Scenario	Participation in meetings to recognize Tabriz: Extensive	Citizenship and tourism customs: Medium	Electronic infrastructure: strong		Climate and geographical location: common
Eleventh Scenario			Electronic infrastructure: strong		
Twelfth Scenario			Hoteling, transportation and leisure centers: strong		
Thirteenth Scenario	Participation in meetings to recognize Tabriz: Extensive	Ancient traditions and history of Tabriz: Excellent	Hoteling, transportation and leisure centers: strong		
Fourteenth Scenario			Electronic infrastructure: strong		
Fifteenth Scenario			Electronic infrastructure: strong		
Sixteenth Scenario		Citizenship and tourism customs: Medium	Hoteling, transportation and leisure centers: strong		

5. Concluding remarks

According to the objectives of the research, the impact of the tourism industry on the urban economy of Tabriz can be predicted according to the existing potentials of tourism in Tabriz and its environmental conditions. On the other hand, the economic development of each region is one of the components of attracting tourists to that region. The correlation analysis and its high result between the variables of economic and tourism consequences of Tabriz show this two-way relationship. According to statistical analysis, the priority of influential factors in the future of Tabriz tourism industry is regional conditions, the existence of historical and cultural potentials, the existence of urban infrastructure and future planning of urban management. It is important to note that despite the favorable situation of Tabriz in the urban and environmental attractions of tourism, the infrastructure has not yet grown in proportion to it and comprehensive and strategic plans for the future of tourism have not been realized. The results of the analysis of research output variables show that the tourism and economic consequences of tourism in Tabriz are moderate. In other words, the outlook for the tourism situation in Tabriz in the continuation of such a situation, both in terms of re-attracting tourists and its economic prosperity will not be very favorable. The low standard deviation of the variables of economic consequences class indicates that there is a consensus among respondents and experts about the inadequacy of the current state of the tourism economy.

The analytical results of the research show that changes in regional conditions and urban potentials do not cause much change in the tourism situation. Because tourists are more concerned with tourism based on their former mental approaches, and the lack of infrastructure and programs is an important factor in the weakness of tourism. The planning variable in this study has the highest score for changing views on tourism and its prosperity. This shows how influential tourism plans and programs can be in the future of the urban economy. Changes in plans and programs simultaneously with the development of infrastructure, can completely change the results of tourism and its economic prosperity and be appropriate to the urban situation of Tabriz. These effects may also show a negative side, when the programs are spent in unnecessary places, the results show that the economic consequence will not be in a good condition.

The consequence of possible scenarios in the future of tourism in Tabriz is the unsuitable economic consequence of this industry in the development of Tabriz and travel to Tabriz as a tourist destination as usual. Realization of plausible scenarios causes balanced economic growth of the region in terms of tourism and destination of Tabriz as one of at least ten tourism hubs of the country among domestic tourists and its introduction as a suitable destination for foreign tourists. Although possible scenarios are less likely to be realized and effective in the real future, but due to the continuity and stability in the management and planning of the tourism industry can provide economic prosperity and tourism polarization in Tabriz.

Based on the research findings, attention to effective management and tourism planning in national and local dimensions based on long-term planning scenario in the national and transnational field for tourism in Tabriz, designing a comprehensive strategic tourism plan in Tabriz by explaining the economic perspective On the long-term planning scenario in the national and transnational sphere for Tabriz tourism, effective modeling of successful cities in tourism, especially in neighboring and touristic countries based on the scenario of effective regional conditions in Tabriz and proximity to tourist countries, local officials pay attention to improving the quality of roads and intercity roads. Based on the scenario of upgrading the physical and communication infrastructure for tourism in Tabriz,

considering that according to the available information, the number of hotels in Tabriz (about 20 hotels) is very small compared to the average of other metropolises, Using the capacity of the private sector and providing the necessary facilities for this sector to improve the quantity and quality of hotels in the city of Tabriz, considering the role of the hotel builder as a supply of tourism industry products based on the scenario of upgrading physical and communication infrastructure for Tabriz tourism Application of university dissertations, articles and research and scientific works done in universities and scientific centers for the development of tourism in Tabriz and attention to its economic consequences based on the scenario of strengthening the cultural and scientific conditions of tourism in Tabriz, Quantitative and qualitative development of tourism-related disciplines, especially tourism economics in Tabriz universities: Based on the scenario of strengthening the cultural and scientific conditions of tourism in Tabriz, introducing ethnic and tribal commonalities in different areas of Tabriz for economic benefit And social aspects of their performance and environment according to the principle of land management based on the scenario of strengthening the regional ethnic and tribal conditions affecting tourism in Tabriz, Comprehensive planning for the development of Tabriz tourism brand due to the existence of various global attractions in Tabriz, including the existence of Tabriz Bazaar in the UNESCO registered works and the location of Tabriz on the Silk Road, based on planning to participate in international forums to recognize Tabriz and Formulation of international tourism marketing strategy and development of cultural and tourism prospects of Tabriz-based destination to attract tourists to the city of Tabriz based on long-term national and transnational planning in the field of tourism in Tabriz, are among the proposals that can be an important step in tourism development. Consequently, have an urban economy.

Conflicts of Interest

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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